

**INVESTIGATION OF FRACTURE PREVENTION EFFECTS OF COMPOSITE
PATCHES REPAIR ON CRACKED ALUMINUM PLATES
EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL STUDY**

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Abstract

Nowadays, composite materials are extensively applicable in various aspects including automotive, marine and most importantly aeronautical engineering because of their excellent characteristics. Innovative maintenance using materials with extraordinary features has led to contributing of composites with the goal of extending their lives services. Glass-epoxy composites are lifesaver, inexpensive and highly practical for repairing the damaged components of aeronautical structures. The present study has employed composite patching technique to repair 50 centrally cracked rectangular aluminum plates subjected uniaxial tensile loading experiment. The 600 KN Santam testing machine used for performing tensile tests. Then, the force-displacement linear graph for each sample was plotted and monitored by its user's software. Next, the Abaqus finite element software simulated the same testing conditions on developed 3D- models using XFEM method. Finally, the numerical and experimental results indicated 0.0266 error percentage between the real and simulated tensile loading tests. In addition, specimens repaired by composite patches whose glass fibers orientations angles are 0,90 proved to have the best optimum performance while those that were repaired by patches with fiber orientations angle -45, +45 had the maximum displacement extension before failure.

Key Words: glass-epoxy composite patching, crack, extended finite element method, aluminum alloy 7075, uniaxial tensile test

1. INTRODUCTION

Makwana and shaikh revealed that the composite patch as an honest method of repair and reinforcement decreases the strain and its intensity [1]. Hosseini et al. concluded glass-epoxy patch repair doubled the fatigue lifetime of two-sided patched specimens [2]. The Composite patching was considered an on spot practical technique for repairing common and regular damages within the aluminum aircraft structures [3]. Impacts of moisture, temperature besides other contributing environmental factors determined to be the varied reasons directly influencing the repair durability of adhesive patching joints [4]. Also, Composite patching proved its capability for underwater repair applications of aluminum structures under tensile and bending loading [5]. Khalid Saeed and Muhammad Abid studied the performances of bonded composite patch as compared to metallic ones on aluminum alloy 2024 samples. They concluded that the fatigue lifetime of the specimens repaired by bonded composite patches enhanced approximately for quarter-hour [6]. Yu Zhiqiang et al. focused on the adhesive repair modification of cracked aluminum samples using carbon-aramid fiber/epoxy sandwich composite patch. It absolutely was found that the composite sandwiches with 3 layers of fibers increased the effectiveness of repair for both tensile and bending loads 86% and 190% respectively [7]. The composite patch repair on aluminum alloy 7075 specimens using graphite-epoxy at high stress levels when applying constant load caused delay in their fatigue life [8]. The rectangular shaped patches found to be more practical compared to oblique and elliptical geometries {[9], [10]}. This study has taken an additional step to analysis the effectiveness of the arrow-shaped composite patch repair experimentally and numerically.

1.1 Methodologies

Both experimental and simulation methods were undertaken to provide accurate and precise data for further analysis of the research.

1.1.2 Experimental Method

In this part of the study, the uniaxial tensile loading test was done on 50 rectangular aluminum alloy 7075 panels of 80 mm width, 150 mm length and 1 mm thick by employing the 600 KN santam testing machine (Figure 1) Each specimen with central crack lengthening 30 mm underwent tensile loading with the speed of 0.2 mm per minute to the failure spot. Single-sided arrow-shaped glass -epoxy composite patches reinforced the cracked panels. Plates positioned vertically between the lower and upper crossheads with 50 mm of gage length in the load-cell (Figure 2). In the next step, the user software of the testing machine was customized with desired geometry, area, length, width, thickness of samples and the required loading type.

Fig.1. The 600 KN Santam Testing Machine

Fig.2. Specimen Positioning in the Load-Cell

English alphabets A to Q were assigned to each category of specimens characterized by following specifications. Alpha is half of an angle between two adjacent right and left sides. SL has been allocated for the length sides of arrow head composite patches. In addition, L represents the horizontal distance as the length and H indicates the height of each composite patch repairs. Table 1 shows the measurements for different patch categories.

Table 1. Measurements for Different Sample Categories

Category	Alpha Angle (degree)	Side Length (mm)	Horizontal Length L (mm)	Vertical Length H (mm)
A	50	30	60	40
B	30	20	55	13
C	53	25	50	40
D	53	25	45	45
E	61.35	30	45	55
F	36	23	55	27
G	40	10	26	13
H	30	13	40	13
I	20	20	55	13
J	40	20	45	25
K	35	23	55	26
L	52	35	65	55
M	40	20	45	25
N	36	23	55	27
O	49	18	55	27
P	20	15	50	10
Q	20	18	50	12

For safety reasons, the security shield of the testing machine was then closed. Tests conducted for several number of specimens of each category to increase the accuracy of experimental results. As tests were being performed, the Force-Displacement curve was plotted by the testing machine user software. The maximum tensile force and extension for all specimens repaired by composite patches with 0,90 to -45, 45 glass fibers orientations were obtained to the failure point (Table 2).

Table 2. Experimental Results for Specimens

Category	Specimen Number	Fibers Orientations (degree)	Max Tensile Load (Newton)	Max Displacement Extension (mm)
A	1	0,90	14583	4.561
A	2	-45,45	11911	3.535
B	1	-45,45	11139	3.250
B	2	0,90	11492	3.343
C	1	0,90	12258	3.642
C	2	-45,45	12258	3.357
D	1	0,90	12405	3.663
D	2	-45,45	11904	3.520
D	3	-45,45	13067	3.673
D	4	-45,45	12302	3.379
D	5	-45,45	12272	3.288
E	1	0,90	12537	3.720
E	2	-45,45	12464	3.705
E	3	-45,45	11640	3.461
F	1	-45,45	11154	2.794
F	2	0,90	10668	3.165
F	3	-45,45	11213	3.346
F	4	0,90	11242	3.336
G	1	0,90	12096	3.618
G	2	-45,45	14406	4.203
G	3	-45,45	13185	3.909
G	4	0,90	9962	2.897
H	1	0,90	9741	2.882
H	2	0,90	9933	2.998
H	3	-45,45	11125	3.297
H	4	-45,45	15583	6.093
I	1	0,90	10345	3.075
I	2	-45,45	11728	3.445
I	3	0,90	12155	3.637
I	4	-45,45	12155	4.756
J	1	0,90	11610	3.465
J	2	-45,45	12464	3.672
J	3	0,90	15936	4.741
K	1	0,90	10036	2.999

K	2	-45,45	11654	3.468
K	3	-45,45	9624	2.853
L	1	0,90	10153	3.043
L	2	-45,45	11345	3.395
M	1	-45,45	8182	2.472
M	2	0,90	8288	2.462
M	3	-45,45	13188	3.897
N	1	0,90	11581	4.510
N	2	-45,45	13405	3.997
N	3	0,90	11213	3.353
N	4	0,90	10786	3.188
O	1	-45,45	13479	3.951
O	2	0,90	14759	4.344
O	3	-45,45	11301	3.337
P	1	-45,45	10271	3.012
P	2	0,90	10536	3.102
Q	1	0,90	10271	3.026
Q	2	-45,45	9830	2.869

1.2. Numerical Simulation

1.2.1 Design of Part

Abaqus finite element software version 6.14 2021 was employed to numerically simulate the tensile loading test. The three-dimensional solid and shell extrusion features were used for the aluminum panel and crack with 30 mm of length. It should be noted that in accordance with experimental results of specimen number 3 of category J, the design of this repair patch considered to have the best and optimum geometry for simulation using the shell planar base feature (Figures 3, 4 & 5).

1.2.2 Property

Fig.3. 2D Plate Sketch

Fig.4. The Crack Sketch

Fig.5. The Patch Sketch

Determination

Real specifications of aluminum alloy 7075 from the literature such as the Young's Modulus and Poisson's Ratio were applied for the panel (Table 3).

Table 3. Material Characteristics of Aluminum Alloy 7075

Layer Name	Poisson's Ratio	Young's Modulus
Aluminum alloy 7075	0.33	71.7 (GPa)

Also, the engineering constants for the glass-epoxy composite patch considered as Table 4 shows.

Table 4. Glass-Epoxy Material Specifications

E1	E2	E3	G12	G13	G23	Nu12	Nu13	Nu23
40e9	10e9	10e9	3.8e9	3.8e9	3.4e9	0.30	0.30	0.40

The condition during which the crack propagated within the aluminum plate and caused failure was reported at maximum principal stress and displacement extension of 524 and 4.741 respectively. The composite layup feature was used in order to set the orientations of patch plies. Then, the plies each thickening 0.5 mm with 0 and 90 rotation angles were positioned. Next, axis 3 (Z) as the local material orientation system was chosen for the composite patch normal (Figure 6).

1.2.3

Fig.6. The Orientation of Patch Plies

Assembling

At this stage, two surfaces titled as the slave and master were assigned to the back of the patch and front of the plate to define the bond between them in interaction module. The central crack positioned with 25 mm of length from each right and left edges on the plate. To repair the specimen, the composite patch placed on the central crack with 17.5 mm of distance from both sides (Figures 7& 8).

Fig.7. Positioning of the Crack

Fig.8. Central Crack on the Plate

1.2.4 Step

The general static procedure and 1 second as time period considered. To apply the extension speed of real testing conditions, 0.2 and 0.002 were chosen for the initial and minimum increment size.

1.2.5 Meshing

To mesh the plate, the hex element shape with linear geometric order was selected. Also, 0.2 absolute value and 2 as the approximate global size were further applied. It should be noted that the employed element shape for the plate was C3D8R (Figure 9).

Fig.9. The Meshed Plate

Partitioning divided the composite patch into two triangular in each side and a separate rectangle in the middle. The structured meshing technique with quad element shape and the linear type of element S4R allocated for the meshing of

rectangular geometry in the center. In addition, the Tri shape and the S3 element type with the same mesh method were assigned to the triangular geometries (Figures 10, 11& 12).

Fig.10. Partitioning of Patch

Fig.12. Fully-Meshed and Repaired Cracked Aluminum Plate

1.2.6 Interactions

The plate front surface was constrained to the back of the patch to create the bond using shell-to-solid coupling feature. The XFEM method was then consequently enabled for the simulation of crack propagation in the specimen (Figures 13 & 14).

Fig.14. The Defined Domain for Crack Propagation

1.2.7 Loading

To define the loading conditions, two sets were created for the end and top of the aluminum plate by node selection. For the boundary conditions, the top-set subjected to Y direction as the only moving degree of freedom. The end-set was considered to be Encastre to simulate the fixed lower crossheads in the testing machine (Figure 15).

1.2.8- Job

In the job module, the simulated repaired plate with glass-epoxy composite patch was submitted for further analysis.

1.2.9- Visualization

The requested field outputs using the numerical results of the simulation are shown as in figure 16.

Fig.15: Defining Boundary Conditions for Tensile Testing

Fig.16. The Distribution of Misses Stress in Cracked Specimen

The force versus displacement extension graph for the composite patch with the optimum performance of repair was then plotted (Figure 17).

Fig.17. The Force-Displacement Curve for the Specimen Number 3 of Category J

The maximum tensile force and extension for specimens of different categories were obtained numerically. To investigate the data validity, the error percentage was calculated by comparing the experimental and numerical results (Tables 5& 6).

Table 5. Comparison of the Numerical and Experimental Results for Sample Categories A to J

Category & Specimen Number	Maximum Numerical Tensile Load	Maximum Experimental Tensile load	Error Percentage
A1	14620	14583	0.0026
A2	11920	11911	0.0008
B1	11329	11139	0.0168
B2	11520	11492	0.0025
C1	12280	12258	0.0018
C2	12280	12258	0.0018
D1	12410	12405	0.0005

Category & Specimen Number	Maximum Numerical Tensile Load	Maximum Experimental Tensile Load	Error Percentage
K1	10121	10036	0.0084
K2	11712	11654	0.0050
K3	9630	9624	0.0007
L1	10257	10153	0.0102
L2	11440	11345	0.0084
M1	8386	8182	0.0244
M2	8339	8388	0.0059
M3	13220	13188	0.0025
N1	11600	11581	0.0017
N2	13570	13405	0.0122
N3	11330	11213	0.0104
N4	10770	10786	0.0015
O1	13480	13479	0.0001
O2	14760	14579	0.0123
O3	11380	11301	0.0070
P1	10390	10271	0.0115
P2	10580	10536	0.0015
Q1	10340	10271	0.0067
Q2	9840	9830	0.0019
D2	11940	11904	0.0031
D3	13130	13067	0.0048
D4	12334	12302	0.0026
D5	12280	12272	0.0007
E1	12520	12537	0.0014
E2	12460	12464	0.0004
E3	11710	11640	0.0060
F1	11180	11154	0.0024
F2	10710	10668	0.0040
F3	11280	11213	0.0060
F4	11360	11242	0.0104
G1	12260	12096	0.0134
G2	14556	14406	0.0104
G3	13210	13185	0.0019
G4	9969	9962	0.0008
H1	9809	9741	0.0070
H2	10204	9933	0.0266
H3	11240	11125	0.0103
H4	15610	15583	0.0018
I1	10450	10345	0.0101
I2	11729	11728	0.0001
I3	12360	12155	0.0166
I4	12190	12155	0.0029
J1	11730	11610	0.0103
J2	12469	12464	0.0005
J3	16089	15936	0.0096

Table 5. Comparison of Numerical and Experimental Results for Sample Categories K to Q

2. Results

1. The data validation between the results obtained from experimental tests and numerical simulations showed maximum 0.0266 of error percentage for XFEM method.
2. The composite patches with glass fibers orientations angles of 0,90 significantly increased the durability of the repair up to 1593 newton.

3. Cracked specimens repaired by patches with -45, 45 degree of glass fibers orientations extended more meanwhile they failed by rise in tensile force.
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3. Discussion and Conclusions

In this study the impacts of composite patch repair with different glass fibers orientation angles on cracked aluminum alloy 7075 plates were investigated. The 600KN Santam testing machine was employed to perform the experimental tensile tests. Then, each of cracked specimen was numerically simulated with Abaqus software using the extended finite element method. The validation of experimentally obtained results indicated the least error percentage in comparison to numerical ones. It has been found out that composite patching technique highly enhance the durability of repair in aluminum structures. Taking everything into consideration, with the aid and contribution of technology, failure of aluminum components is highly predictable under most of the conditions.

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